

Description of the Translation Quality Evaluation (TQE) Task: Fluency and Adequacy

Objective

The objective of this document is to clearly define the instructions for the translation quality evaluation (TQE) task with TAUS-DQF. This evaluation task consists on assessing the Fluency and Adequacy offered by different translations.

Description of the task

1. You will receive an email with the link to the evaluation platform and brief instructions. Clicking the link will redirect you to the evaluation page.
2. On this page, click the "Start" button to start with the evaluation.
3. Below you can see a screenshot of the user interface of the evaluation platform. In the screenshot, you can see the "Source" section with segments in the source language, and the "Target" section with segments in the target language.

TQE Explanation

The screenshot displays the TQE evaluation interface. It is divided into several sections:

- Source (English (United Kingdom))**: Contains a "Start" button, a "Current" segment highlighted in green with the text "Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October", and a "Next" segment with the text "Lagarde stated that interest rate increases will continue to tame inflation."
- Target (Spanish (Spain))**: Contains a "Start" button, a "Current" segment highlighted in green with the text "Inflación récord en la zona euro.", and a "Next" segment with the text "Lagarde confirmó que las subidas de tipos de interés continuarán para acabar con la inflación."
- Fluency:** Includes radio buttons for "Incomprehensible", "Disfluent", "Good", and "Flawless", along with a "(More Info)" link.
- Adequacy:** Includes radio buttons for "None", "Little", "Most", and "Everything", along with a "(More Info)" link.
- Comments:** A text input field with a "Characters left: 500" indicator.
- Metadata:** Shows "Filename: TAUS DQF - Sample for Evaluation.xlsx" and "Segment: 1 of 4".
- Navigation:** "PREVIOUS" and "NEXT" buttons, with "NEXT" being blue and "Or Press Enter" text below it.

4. Segments highlighted in green, next to "Current", are the segments to be evaluated. The segments appearing beside "Next" are the following segments to be evaluated, so you can take contextual information into consideration during your evaluation.
5. You must first read the translation proposal and rate the Fluency (from Incomprehensible to Flawless). Then, you must read the source text and the translation proposal and rate the Adequacy (from None to Everything). Below you can find more detailed information about when you should use each rating for Adequacy and Fluency.
6. Finally, you must press the "Next" button to move to the following segments, until you evaluate all segments.